

Pentzia incana Skaapbossie

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: Up to 30 to 60 cm in height

Distribution:

Skaapbossie/sheep bush is widespread throughout South Africa, Botswana and Namibia. In South Africa, it is found in different biomes and vegetation types, including Succulent Karoo, Nama Karoo, Fynbos and Renosterveld. Preferred habitats are loamy or sandy ridges and plains within arid and semi-arid areas between 900-1700 m above sea level.

Importance:

This species is an important pasture plant in the Karoo. The aromatic compounds in its leaves are thought to contribute to the distinctive flavour of Karoo lamb. It has a unique shallow root system. Its ability to anchor and propagate itself through the root system results in the formation of a dense root mass that binds the soil, reducing erosion. (<https://pza.sanbi.org/pentzia-incana>)

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 288 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 7.39 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 10.41 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.7% [Single: 0.2%, Duplicated: 99.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 2 086.75 kilobases

Contig number: 9 599

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DIPLOMICS

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